

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF DIGITALISATION ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between digitalisation and economic growth in Nigeria using annual time-series data from 1991 to 2024. Digitalisation is proxied by the percentage of internet users, while economic growth is measured by gross domestic product, with gross fixed capital formation, human development index, government effectiveness and inflation included as control variables. The study employed Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) as the main estimation technique and Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) for robustness. The result showed that digitalisation does not yet have a statistically significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria, suggesting that internet usage remains largely concentrated in low-productivity activities. On the other hand, human capital exerts a positive and significant influence on growth, while investment and government effectiveness show weak or adverse effects. The findings highlight the need for policies that deepen productive digitalisation, strengthen human capital development and improve institutional effectiveness to enable digital technologies to contribute meaningfully to Nigeria's long-term economic growth.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Economic Growth, Human Capital, Internet Adoption, Governance

JEL Codes: O33, O40

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is the foremost policy priority for developing countries like Nigeria to raise living standards and alleviate poverty. It involves a sustained expansion in real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita stemming from increased productivity and inputs of labour, capital, and technology (Haller, 2012; Meliantsev, 2023). For low-income economies, achieving rapid economic growth is imperative for economic transformation from reliance on traditional agriculture to modern industrial and service sectors. It enables "catching up" with advanced countries through rising competitiveness (Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 2004). Recent studies have highlighted that in Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, countries that leverage technological adoption alongside human capital development experience more resilient economic growth trajectories (Aleksandrova et al., 2022; Qin & Xu, 2024).

Digitalisation refers to the adoption of digital technologies, which includes information and communication technologies (ICTs), internet penetration, mobile connectivity, and digital platforms, for transforming production, service delivery, and market efficiency (Frey & Osborne, 2017; Garza-Rodriguez, 2020). It enhances innovation, improves productivity, and facilitates access to information and financial services, especially in developing countries

(Jafrin et al., 2021). In Nigeria, digitalisation has grown rapidly in recent years, presenting both opportunities for economic diversification and challenges related to digital divides and infrastructure gaps. Studies suggest that digitalisation is now a key driver of productivity and sectoral growth, particularly in fintech, agriculture, and education (Obiya, 2024; Karacuka et al., 2025).

Digitalisation has the potential to drive economic growth through increased productivity, innovation, and the creation of new markets (Benga & Elhamma, 2024). In developing countries like Nigeria, digitalisation offers opportunities that surpass traditional development and address longstanding socio-economic challenges. Digital technologies can enhance financial inclusion, improve healthcare delivery, boost agricultural productivity, and facilitate access to education and government services (Yina, 2020; Oloyede et al., 2023). Nigeria has made notable progress in digital adoption, with internet penetration reaching 55.4% in 2023 (World Bank, 2023). The country has also witnessed a growth in digital services, particularly in the financial technology (fintech) sector by attracting US\$976,146,000 in funding in 2022 (Gilbert, 2022). However, challenges such as rural-urban digital divides, limited infrastructure, and the high cost of data remain critical bottlenecks (Paul & Victor, 2023; Mura & Donath, 2023).

The role of digitalisation in reshaping economies across countries has been quite unprecedented. The potential for digital technologies to drive economic growth through increased productivity, innovation, and the creation of new markets is well-documented (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Schwab, 2016). Nigeria has witnessed growth in digital entrepreneurship and innovation; however, the specific impact and dynamics of digitalisation on economic growth in Nigeria remain underexplored.

Therefore, this study sought to investigate the impact of digitalisation on economic growth in Nigeria, using recent empirical data to provide to add to the body of knowledge. The paper is structured into five sections. Section 1 presents the introduction, Section 2 reviews related literature, Section 3 outlines the methodology, Section 4 presents and discusses the results and Section 5 concludes with recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

2.1.1 The Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Fred Davis (1989), explains technology adoption through two core constructs: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, which shape users' attitudes, behavioural intentions and actual system usage (Davis, 1989). The model has been widely applied in digitalisation and information systems research, and was later extended to incorporate broader determinants such as social influence and facilitating conditions, particularly through its integration into the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Despite its strengths, TAM has been criticised for oversimplifying the technology adoption process. It assumes largely rational decision-making, focuses primarily on individual users and gives limited attention to wider social, cultural, organisational and economic situation (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Moreover, the model offers limited guidance on how to improve adoption outcomes and does not sufficiently explain post-adoption behaviours such as continued use, resistance or abandonment.

While TAM provides understanding for user perceptions and technology acceptance, its relatively narrow scope constrains its explanatory power in complex digital ecosystems. Nevertheless, it remains relevant for analysing how user acceptance of digital technologies interacts with demographic and economic factors to influence digitalisation-driven economic growth in Nigeria

2.1.2 The Neo-Classical Theory of Growth

The Neo-Classical Theory of Growth, independently developed by Robert Solow (1956) and Swan (1956), explains long-term economic growth through the interaction of capital accumulation, labour inputs and technological progress. Capital accumulation, through investment in machinery, infrastructure and equipment, is viewed as a primary driver of increased production capacity and output (Solow, 1956). The theory also highlights diminishing returns to capital, indicating that additional capital has progressively smaller effects on output over time. Technological progress, considered exogenous in Solow's model, enhances productivity by enabling economies to produce more output from the same inputs (Solow, 1956; Romer, 1986). Later refinements through endogenous growth theory emphasised the role of human capital, R&D, and knowledge spillovers as internal drivers of sustained growth (Romer, 1986; Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 1992).

Labour inputs, including the quantity and quality of the workforce, contribute to growth through human capital development. Investments in education and training increase skills and productivity, linking higher educational attainment to improved economic output (Becker, 1964; Mincer, 1958). The theory also incorporates the convergence hypothesis, suggesting that economies with lower initial per capita income tend to grow faster, catching up with wealthier economies (Baumol, 1986; Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 1992).

The Solow Growth Model operationalises Neo-Classical principles by explicitly modelling how savings, population growth and technological advances interact to determine output over time (Mankiw, 2005). While foundational, the model has limitations: it treats technological progress as exogenous, assumes homogeneous capital and labour and overlooks institutional, policy and environmental factors affecting growth. Despite these constraints, the Neo-Classical framework and Solow model remain highly relevant for analysing how demographic shifts, digitalisation and technological progress influence economic growth in developing countries like Nigeria.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Empirical studies on digitalisation and economic growth have significantly expanded in recent years, indicating the growing role of digital technologies in shaping economic growth across different countries. Existing empirical evidence largely suggests that digitalisation enhances economic growth through improved productivity, efficiency, financial inclusion and innovation. However, the effectiveness of these impacts vary across countries due to differences in institutional structures, technological readiness, human capital and supporting infrastructure. Therefore, a review of the empirical literature is essential to highlight established findings, methodological approaches and existing gaps that justify further investigation, particularly in Nigeria.

In this regard, Benner (2017) examined the effects of cultural acceptance of digitalisation on economic growth of East and West Germany from 2004 to 2014. Cultural acceptance of digitalisation was measured using Google Trend data. The study employed Simple Generalised Least Square (GLS) for data analysis. The result revealed that cultural acceptance of

digitalisation has a greater impact on the economy of East Germany than that of West Germany. This implies that East Germany benefited from the rise of the technology industry in Germany more than West Germany. The study however is not hinged on any theory.

Longe et al. (2020) investigated the role of digitalisation in economic growth in Nigeria using time series data for the period spanning from 2000 to 2019. The focus of study was on the state of digital finance and its impact on economic performance in Nigeria. The study employed a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model to analyse the data. The result revealed that digital finance has significant positive impact on economic growth. Though the study included variables like mobile penetration, internet access and e-commerce but did not take into consideration the issues like digital literacy and cyber security

Omri (2020) evaluated the relationship between technological changes and sustainable development. The study focused on the impact of technological advancements on sustainable across countries with different levels of development. The study adopted panel data regression model, for data analysis. The result revealed that technological innovation has positive impact on sustainable development in developed countries, where the necessary infrastructure and human capital are available, while limited access to digital infrastructure negatively impact on sustainable development in developing countries.

Shibata (2022) examined the changing role of digitalisation in the political economy of Japan. The study further examined the role of technology in the service sector of Japan. The study employed a qualitative approach by interacting with managers in the hospitality industry and union officials. The findings revealed that digitalisation has the potential to improve working conditions and contribute to a more stable form of growth in Japan. The study concludes that digitalisation has contributed positively to the service sector of Japan. However, quantitative approach of data analysis would have been more appropriate for the study.

Kalabikhina and Kazbekova (2022) examined the impact of the first demographic dividend on economic growth considering human capital for the period spanning 1997 to 2017. The study employed a quantitative method of data analysis on the data collected for 74 Regions in Russia. The result revealed that demographic factors have a positive impact on the economic growth of Russia. The study concludes that development of human capital can as well impact the economic development of Russia Region. However, key demographic factors were not captured in the study.

Rajagukguk (2022) investigated the relationship between demographic dividend type and economic features with internet use from 2001–2017 using panel data. The study adopted fixed effects regression models for data analysis. It also used random effects regression model, pooled least square model, and static generalised method of moments for checks of robustness. The result showed that internet use was higher in countries from late- and post- demographic dividend type. Access to electricity, economic growth, and foreign direct investment were found to have a positive relationship with internet use while inflation was found to have negative relationship with internet use. The study however failed to clearly state the countries covered.

Nkwatch (2022) investigated the effect of information and communication technology (ICT) on regional growth in the *Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)* using panel data from 14 member countries over 2007–2021. The study employed a dynamic panel Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to analyse the contributions of ICT, measured by internet connections and mobile phone use, to economic activities and growth across the region. The results showed that ICT penetration significantly contributed to regional economic growth, as greater internet and mobile phone use facilitated capital diffusion, expanded trade activities and strengthened economic linkages among member states. The paper recommended policy

implications such as increasing ICT penetration to support economic expansion and integration within the ECOWAS region.

Leo and Clement (2022) examined the effects of mobile broadband subscriptions on economic growth and employment in Nigeria from 2010 to 2020 using structural equation modelling and GMM estimation techniques. The study aimed to determine how variations in mobile broadband penetration influenced economic performance and labour market outcomes in the country. Findings revealed that mobile broadband significantly influenced economic growth and employment, with effects depending on instrument variables such as population growth, broadband speed, capital stock, financial deepening and crude oil prices. The study also found that improved quality and speed of mobile broadband helped reduce unemployment and enhance labour market outcomes, although the full potential of mobile broadband for growth was yet to be realised in Nigeria.

Aleksandrova et al. (2022) investigated the effect of digitalisation on the economic growth of Russia. The study employed logical-heuristic approach. The result revealed that digitalisation has a positive impact on economic growth of Russia. The study concluded that, though digital innovation is necessary for economic growth since it gives rise to opening borders, the spread of business transparency and publicity principles, and contribute to the ability to resist cyber threats it but digitalization alone is not sufficient for economic growth.

Mura and Donath (2023) examined the impact of digitalisation on the economic growth of the European Union using panel data for a period spanning 2000 to 2021. The study adopted a panel model technique. The study found that digitalisation has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in the EU. The study however failed to provide any theory to support it.

Alao-Owunna et al. (2023) examined the impact of digitalisation on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 2010-2020. The study employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method analysis to investigate how digital technologies which includes mobile internet, e-commerce and digital banking, impact economic growth. The result showed that digitalisation has positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study also noted that infrastructure issues and digital literacy challenges limit the full potential of digital technologies, particularly in rural areas. Though the study included variables such as internet penetration, digital banking adoption and mobile usage but did not consider factors such as cyber threats despite their potential to undermine the effectiveness of digitalisation through increased risk and reduced user confidence.

Alao-Owunna and Adediwura (2023) examine the state of digital transformation and its implications for economic growth in Nigeria for the period 2015 to 2022. The study employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method for data analysis. The result showed that digital transformation has potential to significantly impact economic growth in Nigeria. Variables such as digital infrastructure, internet access and digital technologies adoption were included in the analysis but failed to address issues such digital security.

Oloyede, et al. (2023) investigated the impact of the digital economy in developing countries through a systematic review and meta-analysis of existing empirical studies. The authors systematically collected and evaluated research findings that examined the digital economy's effects on economic growth across various developing economies. Meta-analytic technique was applied to synthesise quantitative results from different studies and assess overall effect sizes, while also identifying patterns and inconsistencies in methodologies. The study found that the digital economy generally had a positive influence on economic growth and related indicators, though the magnitude of effects varied across studies and regions. The study also identified gaps in measurement approaches and recommended more consistent use of robust

econometric methods in future research. However, the paper did not specify the exact number of countries covered in the underlying empirical studies included in the analysis.

Torok (2024) investigated the correlation between digital development and economic growth in the European Union from 2015 to 2020. The study employed Pearson Correlation and F-statistic to analyse the data. The result revealed that the more digitally developed countries had a higher per capita GDP. The study concludes that there is positive relationship between digital development and economic growth in the European Union. The study however is not link with any relevant theory.

Qin and Xu (2024) examined the impact of digital economy on population dividend in China using panel data from 2011 to 2020. The study employed fixed effects regression for data analysis. The result revealed that digital economy has significant positive impact on demographic quality dividend. It also showed that digital economy can as well affect demographic quantity and quality through urbanisation and that digitalisation of economy positively influence demographic quality dividend in China.

Obiya (2024) examined the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the growth of startup enterprises in Nigeria using a mixed-method research design that combined quantitative surveys and qualitative case study data collected from 50 startups operating in sectors such as fintech, healthtech, and agritech. The study applied survey analysis alongside interview data interpretation to assess how the application of AI technologies affected key performance indicators including revenue growth, operational efficiency and customer engagement. Findings showed that startups integrating AI experienced notably higher growth. Despite these positive trends, the study identified infrastructural and financial constraints as significant barriers to broader AI adoption among Nigerian startups.

Sanni and Onakoya (2025) investigated the relationship between human capital development, institutional quality and GDP per capita in Nigeria using annual data from 1989 to 2022. The study used secondary data sourced from the World Bank, the Central Bank of Nigeria and the National Bureau of Statistics. To analyse the data, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing technique to account for mixed orders of integration among the variables was employed. The empirical results showed that government expenditure on education had a positive and statistically significant impact on GDP per capita, whereas government expenditure on health had a significant negative effect over the study period. Additionally, institutional quality was found to have a negative and statistically significant relationship with GDP per capita. Based on the findings, increased public spending on education and health and the adoption of systemic policies to enhance institutional quality in order to improve economic growth was recommended.

Abdur-Raheem et al. (2025) examined the impact of telecommunication infrastructure on economic growth in Nigeria using time-series data from 2001 to 2022. The study analysed the relationship between key telecommunications indicators, such as mobile subscriptions, broadband penetration and related infrastructure variables and real economic growth. For analysis of data, the study adopted Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing technique to determine both short-run and long-run effects. The findings revealed that telecommunication infrastructure has a marginal positive but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth in the long run, while in the short run it had a negative and statistically significant impact on growth.

Karacuka et al. (2025) examined the relationship between digitalisation and labour productivity in 40 Sub Saharan African countries over the period 2006–2021 using panel data. The study developed a composite digitalisation index from ICT indicators including mobile and fixed-line subscriptions, internet usage, and broadband penetration. For analysis, the study applied

generalized least squares (GLS) regression and used system generalized method of moments (GMM) to check for robustness and endogeneity. The findings revealed that digitalisation had limited impact on overall labour productivity, but sector-specific effects were evident: positive in agriculture and manufacturing and negative in the service sector, highlighting a productivity paradox. Additional factors such as political stability, electricity availability, trade openness, and human capital were positively associated with productivity.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study on digitalisation and economic growth in Nigeria employed an *ex post facto* research design. The research analysed time series data from 1991 to 2024 to investigate the impact of digitalisation on economic growth in Nigeria.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

Understanding the drivers of long-run economic growth has remained a central concern in economic theory and policy, particularly for developing economies seeking sustainable development. Classical and neoclassical growth theories emphasise the roles of capital accumulation, labour, and technological progress in shaping growth outcomes. Among these, technological advancement is widely recognised as the key mechanism through which economies achieve sustained increases in productivity and income over time. This study is anchored on the neoclassical growth theory, specifically the Solow growth model (Solow, 1956), which posits that while capital and labour accumulation can drive growth in the short run, long-run economic growth is fundamentally determined by technological progress. In the Solow framework, improvements in technology enhance total factor productivity, allowing economies to produce more output from given levels of capital and labour. Subsequent extensions of the model, particularly the augmented Solow model proposed by Mankiw et al. (1992), further highlight the importance of human capital in reinforcing the growth effects of technological change. Within this theoretical context, digitalisation is conceptualised as a modern manifestation of technological progress. The adoption of digital technologies, proxied by internet usage enhances economic efficiency by reducing transaction costs, improving information flows, fostering innovation, and increasing the productivity of both capital and labour. Rather than acting as a direct factor of production, digitalisation operates through the technology channel by raising total factor productivity and shifting the production frontier outward. Accordingly, aggregate output in the economy is represented by the standard Cobb-Douglas production function;

$$Y_t = A_t K_t^\alpha L_t^{1-\alpha} \tag{3.1}$$

Where Y_t denotes real output (GDP), K_t represents physical capital, L_t denotes labour, and A_t captures the level of technology or total factor productivity. In this study, the technology parameter A_t is assumed to be influenced by the degree of digitalisation in the economy, as well as by institutional quality and macroeconomic stability. To translate this theoretical framework into an empirically testable form, technological progress is modelled as a function of digitalisation and other growth conditioning factors as given in *Equations 3.2*.

3.3 Model Specification

The study examined the impact digitalisation on economic growth in Nigeria. The model is specified as:

$$GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 DIGI_t + \alpha_2 GFCF_t + \alpha_3 INF_t + \alpha_4 HDI_t + \alpha_5 GOV_t + \mu_{1t} \tag{3.12}$$

Where GDP (proxy for economic growth), DIGI denotes digitalisation (measured by percentage of people using internet), GFCF denotes gross fixed capital formation (proxied by physical capital investment), INF denotes inflation, HDI denotes human development index and GOV denotes government effectiveness, μ is the error term while t denoting time; α_0 is constant; and α_{1-8} are the coefficients of the variables. The inclusion of GDP (economic growth), demographic dividend (DD), gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), inflation (INF), human development index (HDI), and government effectiveness in the model is justified by their roles in influencing investment, productivity and overall economic performance. The inclusion of INF, HDI and GOV is to account for macroeconomic stability, human capital quality and institutional effectiveness respectively.

The study includes GFCF, HDI, GOV, and INF as control variables based on the Solow (1956) and augmented Solow (Mankiw et al., 1992) growth frameworks. GFCF captures physical capital accumulation, HDI proxies human capital, GOV reflects institutional and policy factors, and INF represents macroeconomic stability. These variables are theoretically linked to growth and potentially interact with digitalisation. To address potential endogeneity and simultaneity bias between digitalisation and economic growth, the study employs FMOLS and DOLS estimators, which provide consistent and unbiased long-run coefficient estimates in the presence of cointegration.

Table 3.1: Measurement of Variables and Sources of Data

Variable	Description of Variable	Measurement of Variable	Sources of Data
GDP	GDP: Represents the annual GDP, expressed in current U.S. dollars	Annual GDP expressed in current U.S. dollars	World Bank, 2024
DIGI	Digitalisation: The level of internet usage and digital integration among the population	Percentage of individuals using the internet.	World Bank, 2024
GFCF	Gross Fixed Capital Formation: Contribution of gross fixed capital formation to economic growth	Gross fixed capital formation as a percentage of GDP	CBN, 2024
HDI	Human Capital: Key human development achievements, including education and health	Human Development Index (HDI)	UNDP, 2024
INF	Inflation: Changes in consumer prices over time	Annual percentage change in the Consumer Price Index (CPI)	CBN, 2024
GOV	Government effectiveness : the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)	Perceptions of the quality of governance	World Bank, 2024

Source: Author compilation, 2025

3.4 Estimation Techniques

This study employed an econometric approach to analyse the economic implications of the relationship between digitalisation and economic growth in Nigeria. Initially, a pre-estimation assessment was conducted using descriptive statistics to effectively describe and summarise

data properties, allowing for an understanding of the data distribution. Next, unit root tests were applied to establish the preliminary characteristics of the dataset. Based on the pre-estimation results, a Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) technique was employed to analyse for the analysis while Dynamic OLS (DOLS) serves as a robustness check.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of the data set, giving an indication of the pattern, movements and general behaviour of the variables used in this study over the period covered by the study (1991-2024). The wide range between the minimum and maximum values suggests that the economy has experienced significant swings in growth rates during the study period, driven by oil price shocks, macroeconomic reforms, and economic downturns. This high degree of dispersion suggests that Nigeria’s economic growth has been unstable and susceptible to external shocks, including global commodity price fluctuations, fiscal deficits and exchange rate instability.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	DIGI	GFCF	HDI	GOV	INF
Mean	2.73E+11	12.848	15732.0	0.4811	14.693	19.438
Maximum	5.74E+11	45.500	82889.2	0.5600	20.588	76.800
Minimum	5.21E+10	0.0088	285.59	0.3830	8.6124	0.2000
Std. Dev.	1.65E+11	14.280	21469.7	0.0573	3.1307	16.614
Skewness	0.107788	0.7424	1.8142	-0.3204	0.0121	2.0348
Kurtosis	1.598570	2.2214	5.1917	1.7112	2.3769	6.5681
Jarque-Bera	2.848180	3.9827	25.458	2.9349	0.5507	41.500
Probability	0.240727	0.1365	0.0000	0.2305	0.7593	0.0000
Observations	34	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

4.2 Test for multicollinearity

In order to check for multicollinearity among the independent variables, the variance Inflation factor (IVF) was conducted. This was reported in Table 4.2. It is evidence from the result of the VIF that no correlation exist among the variables, making the result of this study reliable.

Table 4.2: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
DIGI	1.35	0.741
GFCF	1.44	0.694
HDI	1.18	0.847
INF	1.14	0.877
GOV	1.03	0.971
Mean VIF	1.24	

Source: Authors Computation, 2026.

VIF values above 10 typically indicate problematic multicollinearity. As shown in Table 4.2, all VIF values are below 2, with an average VIF of 1.24, indicating no presence of multicollinearity. This suggests that the independent variables are not correlated, reducing the risk of inflated standard errors and unreliable regression coefficients.

4.3. Unit Root Test Results

Prior to the estimation of long-run models, this subsection presents and discusses the results of the unit root tests employed to ascertain the order of integration of the variables. To improve the robustness of the empirical results, both the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) and Kwiatkowski–Phillips–Schmidt–Shin (KPSS) tests were conducted in this study. The findings from Table 4.2 indicate that all variables in levels; economic growth (GDP), demographic dividend (DD), digitalisation (DIGI), investment (GFCF), human capital (HDI), governance (GOV) and inflation (INF), are non-stationary as they have time-varying means and variances. On the other hand, first differencing all variables, all series became stationary, meaning all variables in this study are integrated of order one (I(1)). From the methodological perspective, the fact that all variables are integrated of the same order (I (1)) meets one of the necessary conditions for the Johansen cointegration test and by extension, the estimation of long-run models such as FMOLS and DOLS.

Table 4.3: Unit Root Test Result

Variables	ADF Test			KPSS Test		Inference
	Levels	1 st Difference	Inference	Levels	1 st Difference	
GDP	-1.757083 (-2.957110)	-3.181617 (-2.957110)	1(1)	0.613551 (0.463000)	0.319804 (0.463000)	1(1)
DD	0.134019 (-3.557759)	-5.051734 (-3.557759)	1(1)	0.502675 (0.463000)	0.318974 (0.463000)	1(1)
DIGI	0.013197 (-3.552973)	-3.597012 (-3.557759)	1(1)	0.208069 (0.146000)	0.068888 (0.146000)	1(1)
GFCF	2.495821 (-2.981038)	-3.846646 (-2.976263)	1(1)	0.597106 (0.463000)	0.344063 (0.463000)	1(1)
HDI	0.819288 (-3.552973)	-3.865434 (-3.557759)	1(1)	0.182180 (0.146000)	0.132664 (0.146000)	1(1)
GOV	-3.435739 (-3.552973)	-7.286671 (-3.557759)	1(1)	0.157909 (0.146000)	0.034018 (0.146000)	1(1)
INF	-1.863408 (-3.552973)	-4.994468 (-3.557759)	1(1)	0.157602 (0.146000)	0.071361 (0.146000)	1(1)

Figures in parenthesis represents the critical values at the 5% level

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

4.4: Cointegration Test Results

Having confirmed that all variables are stationary at first difference, this section presents the results of the Johansen cointegration test to examine the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among them. The test is appropriate for this multivariate model where several variables are integrated of the same order. Using trace statistics to determine the number of cointegrating equations, the results in Table 4.6 reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration

at the 5% level. Specifically, the trace statistic indicates up to four cointegrating equations, while the maximum eigenvalue test confirms at least three long-run relationships among economic growth (GDP), digitalisation (DIGI), investment (GFCF), human capital (HDI), governance (GOV), and inflation (INF).

Table 4.4: Johansen Cointegration Result

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.883494	199.1292	125.6154	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.763788	130.3352	95.75366	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.667595	84.15845	69.81889	0.0024
At most 3 *	0.467659	48.91363	47.85613	0.0396
At most 4	0.394138	28.73857	29.79707	0.0658
At most 5	0.308442	12.70327	15.49471	0.1262
At most 6	0.027776	0.901404	3.841465	0.3424

Trace test indicates 4 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level; **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025.

The rejection of the null hypothesis across several lags confirms cointegration and a stable long-run relationship among the variables despite short-term fluctuations. This validates the use of FMOLS and DOLS for long-run estimation and indicates that Nigeria’s digital, and macroeconomic indicators move together under a common long-run equilibrium.

4.5. Analysis of the Effect of Digitalisation on Economic Growth

Table 4.5 reports the long-run estimates of the effect of digitalisation on economic growth in Nigeria using FMOLS as the baseline estimator and DOLS for robustness. Digitalisation (DIGI), measured by the percentage of internet users, does not exhibit a statistically significant effect on economic growth in either specification. The FMOLS estimate yields a negative coefficient (-0.0138; p = 0.4599), while the DOLS estimate produces a positive coefficient (0.0120; p = 0.3443). In both cases, the p-values exceed conventional significance levels, indicating that the estimated effects are not statistically distinguishable from zero. Accordingly, the results do not provide empirical evidence of a long-run growth effect of digitalisation over the sample period. Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) is also statistically insignificant in both models, suggesting that its long-run contribution to growth is not supported within this specification. Human capital (HDI) displays a positive and statistically significant coefficient in both estimations. It is significant at the 5% level under FMOLS (p = 0.0182) and at the 10% level under DOLS (p = 0.0565). This indicates that improvements in human development are associated with higher economic growth in the long run, and the result remains robust across estimators.

Table 4.5: Results of the Effect of Digitalisation on Economic Growth in Nigeria

Variable	FM-OLS				D-OLS			
	Coef.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Coef.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
Constant	21.121***	2.0368	10.3697	0.0000	24.685***	1.5714	15.7088	0.0000
DIGI	-0.0138	0.0184	-0.7497	0.4599	0.0120	0.0121	0.9927	0.3443
GFCF	-0.2255	0.3658	-0.6166	0.5426	-0.2194	0.1706	-1.2859	0.2274
HDI	19.2292**	7.6515	2.5131	0.0182	9.8721*	4.5795	2.1556	0.0565
GOV	-0.8455*	0.4268	-1.9807	0.0579	-0.7878*	0.3579	-2.2010	0.0523
INF	0.0440	0.1082	0.4072	0.6870	0.1721*	0.0942	1.8275	0.0976
R-squared	0.7135				0.9734			
Adj. R-squared	0.6605				0.9202			
Long-run variance	0.2557				0.0222			

*, **, and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Governance (GOV) is statistically significant at the 10% level in both models (FMOLS $p = 0.0579$; DOLS $p = 0.0523$). The negative coefficient suggests that deterioration in governance quality is associated with lower economic growth, consistent with theoretical expectations regarding institutional performance. Inflation (INF) is insignificant under FMOLS but weakly significant at the 10% level in the DOLS model ($p = 0.0976$), indicating limited robustness of its long-run effect. The consistency of key results across FMOLS and DOLS supports the stability of the long-run relationships. The empirical evidence identifies human capital and governance as statistically supported determinants of economic growth, while digitalisation does not exhibit a significant long-run effect within the study period.

The finding that digitalisation does not have a statistically significant long-run effect on economic growth in Nigeria agrees with previous studies (Jafrin et al., 2022; Garza-Rodriguez, 2021; Frey & Osborne, 2017), which highlight that digital technologies alone may not enhance growth unless supported by complementary infrastructure, skilled human capital, and institutional quality. In contrast, the statistically significant effects of human capital and governance observed in this study align with the broader literature, underscoring the central role of education, health, and institutional quality as key determinants of long-run economic performance in developing countries.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.

This study examined the long-run relationship between digitalisation and economic growth in Nigeria using FMOLS and DOLS estimators. The findings showed that digitalisation does not have a statistically significant long-run effect on economic growth over the study period. This suggests that expanding internet access alone is insufficient to drive sustained economic performance. In contrast, human capital and governance emerged as significant determinants of long-run growth. Improvements in education, health and institutional quality were found to positively influence economic growth, while weak governance undermines growth prospects.

These results indicate that Nigeria's growth challenge is less about digital access and more about strengthening the structural conditions that allow digital technologies to translate into productive outcomes.

Based on these findings, Nigeria's digital strategy should move from largely consumption-based internet usage toward productive applications in manufacturing, agriculture, education and finance. The Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovation and Digital Economy and the Nigerian Communications Commission should prioritise reliable broadband infrastructure and policies that promote digital adoption in productive sectors rather than social usage alone. At the same time, the Federal Ministry of Education should deepen digital skills development and technical training, while the Federal Ministry of Health strengthens healthcare systems to improve overall human development. Finally, stronger institutional accountability and regulatory consistency, supported by the National Assembly and anti-corruption agencies, are essential to create an enabling environment where digitalisation can meaningfully support long-term economic growth

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